

Status And Trend Of Seychelles Coral Reefs: 2026

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Prepared for the Seychelles Climate Change Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)

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Foreword

Seychelles' coral reefs are among our most valuable natural assets. They are central to the health of our marine environment and make an essential contribution to biodiversity, livelihoods, tourism, coastal protection, and the resilience of our islands and communities.

Protecting this natural wealth becomes ever more important as our understanding of reef ecosystems deepens, and the pressures acting upon them grow more intense. Like coral reefs around the world, those in the Seychelles are increasingly affected by climate change and a range of local and global stresses. In this context, the need for accurate information, effective monitoring, and coordinated action has never been greater. Addressing key stressors, including pollution and overfishing, will be essential to safeguarding these ecosystems in the long term.

This report marks an important step in advancing the national understanding of coral reef status across Seychelles. By bringing together data, scientific knowledge, and stakeholder contributions, it provides a stronger foundation for informed decision-making and more effective management. It also reflects the value of collaboration, shared commitment, and collective effort in responding to the challenges facing our reefs.

The findings of this report will help inform national dialogue, support practical action, and strengthen the long-term protection and sustainable management of Seychelles' coral reef ecosystems. They also reinforce the importance of integrating coral reef conservation into wider national priorities, strengthening coordination across sectors, and maintaining continued attention to the key pressures affecting reef health. Sustained collaboration among government, local communities, civil society, the private sector, and research institutions remains key in ensuring that the knowledge presented in this report is translated into meaningful and lasting action.

The effective implementation of the report's recommendations requires continued commitment, adequate resourcing, technical expertise, and strong institutional coordination. Equally important will be the strengthening of national monitoring efforts, regular review of progress, and the ability to respond adaptively as new knowledge and evidence emerge. In this way, the report can serve not only as a record of current reef status but also as a foundation for continued learning, accountability, and improved management over time.

Reliable science and clear evidence are essential to good management. Reports such as this do more than describe status and trends; they help guide planning, encourage informed discussion, and support meaningful action. They also remind us that the future of our reefs is closely linked to the well-being of our people and to the sustainable development of our country.

I extend my sincere appreciation to all partners, institutions, experts, and stakeholders who contributed to this work. Their dedication and collaboration have made this report possible. It is my hope that this report will serve as a valuable resource in guiding continued efforts to protect the long-term health and resilience of Seychelles' coral reefs for the benefit of present and future generation.

Hon. Marie-May Jeremie
**Minister for Environment, Climate,
Energy and Natural Resources**

Message from the Implementing Partner

SeyCCAT is honoured to have facilitated this consultancy on the behalf of the Seychelles and with the Ministry for Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resources, partners, experts, and stakeholders.

This report is a key step in strengthening the understanding of Seychelles' coral reefs. By collating long-term datasets, knowledge, and stakeholder input, Seychelles is positioned to take evidence-based decisions and coordinated action.

SeyCCAT remains committed to supporting partnerships and action on this report's recommendations and Seychelles' wider biodiversity and resilience goals.

We encourage active engagement from policymakers, agencies and partners through collaboration, implementation, and the sharing of expertise. Together, we can promote effective conservation and collective progress toward our national goals.

We thank all contributors and trust this report will guide continued efforts to safeguard Seychelles' coral reefs.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Helena Sims'.

Helena Sims
Chief Executive Officer, SeyCCAT

Credit: Image courtesy of Chris Mason Parker
Tourism Department

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List of Contributors

This report was collectively developed through contributions from a wide range of partners involved in coral reef monitoring, data acquisition, data analysis, meetings, workshops, chapter development and technical review. Contributor roles were structured using the CRediT (Contributor Role Taxonomy)¹ framework. The credit table system used for contributor roles is provided in the Annex 3 and detailed list of contributors by institution is list below:

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- The Nature Conservancy (TNC):** Helena Sims.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP):** Daig Romain.
- WiseOceans:** Georgina Beresford, Ashley Harding, Oliver Lee, Caitlin Rendell.

¹ National Information Standards Organization. (2022). The Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT). ANSI/NISO Z39.104-2022. <https://credit.niso.org/>

List of Acronyms and Symbols

Acronyms

AIMS	Australian Institute of Marine Science
BERI	Blue Economy Research Institute
CRedit	Contributor Role Taxonomy
DHW	Degree Heating Week
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
GCRMN	Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network
GFCR	Global Fund for Coral Reefs
GVI	Global Vision International
ICRI	International Coral Reef Initiative
ICS	Island Conservation Society
MCSS	Marine Conservation Society Seychelles
MECENR	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource
MoFAEB	Ministry of Fisheries, Agriculture & Blue Economy
MPAs	Marine Protected Areas
SD	Standard deviation
SE	Standard error
SeyCCAT	Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust
SFA	Seychelles Fisheries Authority
SIF	Seychelles Islands Foundation
SMSP	Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan
SOSF-DRC	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre
SPGA	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority
SST	Sea surface temperature
TNC	The Nature Conservancy
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WIO	Western Indian Ocean

Symbols

%	Percent
~	Approximately
≥	Greater than or equal to
<	Less than
±	Plus/minus
°C	Degrees Celsius
km ²	Square kilometres
m	Metres
n	Sample size / number of monitored sites

Executive Summary

This report provides a harmonised national assessment of coral reef condition in Seychelles, based on records contributed by 11 dataset providers, covering 285 unique survey sites and 3,778 observations collected between 1994 and 2025. Together, these records provide a 32-year evidence base, representing the longest coral reef monitoring time series currently available at national scale in Seychelles. The report establishes an updated national baseline for coral reef status reporting and management, while also highlighting the uneven distribution of monitoring effort across the five archipelago groups used in the analysis: Inner Islands, Aldabra Group, Amirantes Group, Alphonse Group, and Farquhar Group.

Thermal stress remains the dominant national-scale pressure on Seychelles reefs. Degree Heating Week records show repeated episodes of major heat stress exceeding 8 °C-weeks DHW in 1998, 2010, 2016, 2019, 2020, 2024, and 2025. Among these, 2024 stands out as the most severe thermal-stress year in the available record. These results show that Seychelles reefs are exposed to recurrent climate-driven disturbance, but also that reef response is not uniform across the country.

At national scale, the overall trend in live hard coral cover is declining. Live hard coral cover was low in the mid-2000s, recovered progressively through the late 2000s and early 2010s, then declined sharply in 2016–2017 following severe bleaching. Partial recovery was recorded after 2018, but this improvement was reversed after 2023, with national mean live hard coral cover declining again in 2024 and 2025. The latest reported year for live hard coral cover in the dataset is 2025, and the latest estimated national mean live hard coral cover is approximately 14%. Paired-site comparisons confirm this recent downturn: reefs showed measurable recovery during the post-2016 period prior to 2024, but matched-site analyses indicate renewed decline consistent with the widespread heat stress recorded in 2024.

The Inner Islands remain central to the national picture because they provide the most continuous long-term monitoring dataset. They show substantial recovery after earlier disturbance, but also marked declines after major bleaching, with recent evidence indicating that gains made before 2024 were not sustained into 2025. The Aldabra Group shows a similar disturbance–recovery trajectory, with steady recovery through 2023 followed by a sharp decline in 2024. The Amirantes Group shows moderate but unstable coral cover, with recovery potential evident on some reefs but strong spatial variability and recent uncertainty. In contrast, the Alphonse Group stands out as the strongest coral-cover system in the national dataset, maintaining comparatively high coral cover despite recent bleaching, although this apparent resilience remains spatially uneven and should be interpreted cautiously. The Farquhar Group is the most data-limited archipelago.

Overall, this report provides a robust national baseline for coral reef status assessment in Seychelles. At the same time, it shows that live hard coral cover alone is not sufficient to fully understand reef condition or recovery potential. Future national reporting would be strengthened by integrating additional indicators such as coral recruitment, macroalgal abundance, fish biomass, structural complexity, and deeper reef habitats, which remain underrepresented in the current monitoring framework. The report therefore serves both as a national status assessment and as a foundation for more coordinated, ecosystem-based coral reef monitoring and management in Seychelles.

Data Coverage

11 dataset providers
285 survey sites
3,778 observations
32-years monitoring period.

Thermal Stress Events

Dominant national-scale pressure on Seychelles reefs. 2024 most severe thermal-stress year.

National Coral Cover

Overall trend in live hard coral cover is declining. Mean coral cover estimated at 14%.

Archipelago Comparison

Most show a pattern of recovery followed by 2024 decline. Alphonse shows the greatest resilience; Farquhar remains data-deficient.

Missing indicators Gap

Needed national reporting in:
Coral recruitment, macroalgae,
fish biomass, structural complexity,
deep reefs habitat.

Introduction

Seychelles' coral reefs are critical ecosystems that supports biodiversity, fisheries, tourism and coastal protection, but the latest national evidence indicates a declining trajectory under recurrent thermal stress and persistent local pressures.

Coral reefs are among the most important marine ecosystems in Seychelles, providing ecological, social and economic benefits at national scale. Within the country's Exclusive Economic Zone of approximately 1.35 million km², coral reefs are estimated to cover between 1,694 and 1,935 km². This ecosystem supports shoreline protection, fisheries production, tourism activity and wider marine biodiversity. Their national importance is further reflected in marine governance, with more than 95% of Seychelles' coral reefs estimated to occur within protected areas under the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan.

Seychelles coral reefs have experienced three major climate-mediated thermal stress events: in 1998, 2016 and, most recently, in 2024 during the Fourth Global Coral Bleaching Event (Reimer et al., 2024). In the Inner Seychelles, the 1998 event caused an estimated 90% loss of live coral (Engelhardt, 2004, Goreau, 2000) and reduced coral cover to around 3%, while the 2016 event also resulted in severe bleaching and mortality under heat stress that exceeded 1998 levels (Graham et al., 2024). This pattern is consistent with broader evidence that coral bleaching and marine heatwaves have become increasingly frequent and severe over recent decades (Sully et al., 2019). If this intensification continues, recovery windows may become too short for many reefs to re-establish coral dominance between successive disturbances, increasing the likelihood of coral-algal regime shifts, structural degradation and eventual ecosystem collapse. In the Western Indian Ocean, Obura et al. (2021) concluded that the cumulative and synergistic effects of increasing local and global stressors may leave only a few decades before these ecosystems collapse.

This report is situated within the broader framework of coral reef status assessment developed through the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN) under the International Coral Reef Initiative (ICRI). At global level, the GCRMN provides the main structure for periodic assessment and reporting on the condition of the world's coral reefs. In the Western Indian Ocean, this reporting framework has been advanced through collaboration among the GCRMN, the Nairobi Convention Coral Reef Task Force, CORDIO and the Indian Ocean Commission, linking national monitoring efforts to regional syntheses. Important milestones in this process include the Coral Reef Status Report for the Western Indian Ocean published in 2017, which updated previous GCRMN reporting cycles through a regional synthesis across nine countries, and the Western Indian Ocean chapter of Status of Coral Reefs of the World: 2020 (Obura et al., 2017, Souter et al., 2021). Seychelles has contributed to these regional and global reporting processes over time. At the same time, these assessments have highlighted the continuing need for stronger national data management, archiving, harmonisation and routine reporting. In this context, the present report represents a further step in the development of a national coral reef reporting pathway for Seychelles, with the aim of consolidating dispersed monitoring records into a single, standardised evidence base document.

At national level, this work directly supports implementation of the Seychelles National Policy and Strategic Action Plan on Coral Reef Conservation and Management. Work Programme 3 of the policy calls for management-oriented monitoring and research on coral reef ecosystems, while Activity 3.1.1 specifically prioritises the standardisation of national coral reef monitoring and reporting. The policy also calls for a nationally coordinated coral reef inventory, stronger inter-organisational coordination, improved baselines, regular reporting, and mechanisms to facilitate submission of key monitoring data to Government. Accordingly, this report and its accompanying database are intended not only as scientific outputs, but also as practical tools to support implementation of the national coral reef policy framework.

This work was funded through the Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR) and the Seychelles OCEAN'S RESOLVE Programme managed by SeyCCAT. The GFCR is a United Nations multi-partner trust fund dedicated to SDG 14 and designed to mobilise grant and investment capital for coral reef conservation, resilience and reef-dependent communities. In Seychelles, OCEAN'S RESOLVE was launched in 2024 to support the protection, conservation and restoration of coral reef ecosystems through stronger coordination among government, communities, businesses and conservation organisations. Within this wider programme context, the present report provides a national knowledge product to support evidence-based planning, coordination and long-term reef management.

The database submitted alongside this report is the most comprehensive harmonised coral reef status dataset yet compiled for Seychelles. The consolidated hard coral cover database spans the period 1994–2025 and integrates 11 contributing datasets, 285 unique survey sites across the full EEZ. The report analyses data from multiple institutions and monitoring approaches. In doing so, it provides the Government of Seychelles and partner institutions with robust evidence-base tools for national synthesis, future reporting and management-oriented decision-making.

This report has two main objectives:

- 1) To aggregate and analyse datasets from multiple monitoring programmes in order to provide national evidence base on coral reef condition in Seychelles.
- 2) To present current estimates and long-term trends in coral reef condition at both national and archipelago scales, in a format that supports management, policy and future monitoring coordination.

Geographic Information And Context

KEY NUMBERS

EEZ Extent: **Approx. 1,350,000 km²**

Estimated coral reef extent: from **1694 km² to 1935 km²**

Area of Coral Reef under Protection: from **92% to 95%**

The Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of the Seychelles hosts approximately 1,935 km² of coral reef habitat, representing 12.7% of the coral reefs of the wider Western Indian Ocean (WIO) region (Souter et al., 2021). Under the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan, more than 95% of coral reefs are estimated to fall within designated protected areas (Government of Seychelles, 2025). This includes 18.5% in strict no-take zones, SMSP Zone 1 and other pre-SMSP existing MPAs, with the remainder managed as Zone 2: Sustainable Use Areas (Government of Seychelles, 2025) (Annex 1). The Republic of Seychelles comprises 115 islands distributed across two main island systems: the more populous and predominantly granitic Inner Islands, and the remote coralline Outer Islands. For reporting purposes, the Outer Islands are further divided into four geographic groups: Aldabra, Alphonse, Amirantes, Farquhar, reflecting broad spatial structure within the archipelago (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of the Seychelles EEZ showing the five archipelago groups used in this report as the primary geographic units for coral reef status and trend analysis: Inner Islands, Amirantes Group, Alphonse Group, Farquhar Group and Aldabra Group.

Coral reefs in Seychelles are monitored by multiple institutions at different spatial and temporal scales, ranging from repeated fixed-site monitoring programmes to island-specific assessments, rapid bleaching surveys, and broader archipelago-level compilations. Monitoring effort is therefore uneven among islands, habitats, years, and seasons, and datasets differ in survey frequency, timing, and disturbance context. To support a coherent national assessment, this report uses the geographic archipelago group as the principal unit for describing coral reef status and trends. This approach reduces fine-scale inter-island variability associated with monitoring timing, seasonal changes, thermal disturbance dynamics, and environmental heterogeneity, while still retaining the main spatial patterns in reef condition across Seychelles. However, no monitoring data were made available for Ile Platte and Coëtivy, or for the Northern Mahé Plateau coralline islands, namely Denis and Bird. Consequently, no status assessment or trend analysis could be undertaken for these island groups in the present report.

Summary Of Data Contributed To This Report

KEY NUMBERS

Number of dataset providers: **11**

Number of Unique Sites: **285**

Number of Observations: **3778**

Longest time series: **32 years**

Database summary

The consolidated hard coral cover dataset compiled for this report spans from 1994 to 2025 and comprises five archipelago-group time series. In total, the consolidated dataset incorporates 11 contributing datasets, 285 unique survey sites, and 3,778 observations. The longest site record extends across the full 32-year timespan, although the longest yearly repeated time series with data is 11 years. Collectively, these data provide a basis for national comparison of coral cover status and trajectory, but monitoring effort is uneven among archipelago groups in both temporal continuity and sampling intensity.

Coverage

The Inner Islands provide the broadest and most heterogeneous dataset, with 145 unique sites and nine contributing datasets spanning from 1994 to 2025. Monitoring in this group is distributed across several contributors. The Aldabra Group and Amirantes Group provide the most coherent repeated monitoring among the outer islands. These two archipelago groups are the strongest Outer Island time series after the Inner Islands, although they differ in structure: Amirantes integrates two datasets across 2011–2024 and 43 sites, whereas the Aldabra Group comprises a consistent annual monitoring series from 2014 to 2024 at 12 sites in Aldabra, together with a single snapshot survey of 18 sites in Cosmoledo conducted in 2014. Alphonse contributes a smaller but still informative record, across 34 sites between 2009 and 2024, while Farquhar remains the most data-limited compilation, with only four monitored years between 2001 and 2019.

Temporality

The temporal structure of monitoring differs markedly among archipelago groups. The Inner Islands provide the longest national record, but monitoring effort is highly variable through time, with particularly strong coverage during 2005–2015 and renewed contributions in 2022 and 2025. The monitoring within the Aldabra Group shows the strongest annual continuity, with repeated observations in every year from 2014 to 2024 and broadly stable site coverage from 2015 onwards. Amirantes also shows relatively good continuity from 2011 to 2024, although coverage declines sharply in 2018–2019 and no data are available for the year 2020 and 2021. By contrast, the Alphonse Group and Farquhar Group are represented by more discontinuous series with substantial gaps and should therefore be interpreted as intermittent status snapshots rather than uninterrupted trajectories.

Seasonality of monitoring

Within-year timing of monitoring is also uneven and has implications for comparability. Within the Aldabra Group, the SIF monitoring is undertaken in November, providing strong seasonal consistency. Amirantes Group is likewise heavily concentrated in November, with limited supplementary monitoring in October and only minor contributions in other months. Farquhar Group is dominated by March surveys, with only a single October contribution. Alphonse Group shows a more mixed seasonal pattern, with effort concentrated in April, February and December. The Inner Islands display the broadest spread across the calendar year, although monitoring remains strongly weighted towards April, with secondary peaks in November and May. As a result, the national compilation is seasonally coherent within some archipelago groups, but less standardised across the full dataset.

Taken together, the dataset provides robust comparative coverage across Seychelles reef systems, but evidential strength is not uniform. The Inner Islands offer the broadest but most heterogeneous long-term record, Aldabra Group and parts of the Amirantes Group provide the most coherent repeated monitoring, and Alphonse Group and Farquhar Group in particular remain more discontinuous and should be interpreted with greater caution.

Status Of The Coral Reef In Seychelles

KEY NUMBERS

Major thermal stress (>8 °C-weeks DHW): **1998, 2010, 2016, 2019, 2020, 2024 and 2025**

Most severe thermal-stress year in the available record: **2024**

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2025**

Latest estimated national mean live hard coral cover: **14 %**

Trend in national live coral cover: **Declining**

Since the 1998 mass coral bleaching event, coral reef monitoring in Seychelles has expanded substantially, in line with the wider increase in global reef monitoring triggered by that disturbance. As a result, national database was strongest from the mid-2000s onwards, when new monitoring programmes were established and earlier efforts were maintained or reactivated, often in response to successive bleaching events. The available data show that recent coral reef status in Seychelles cannot be understood as a single national trajectory, but rather as a set of contrasting archipelago-specific responses to recurrent thermal stress.

Thermal Stress

Across the Seychelles, the Degree Heating Week (DHW) series indicates major thermal stress above 8 °C-weeks in 1998, 2010, 2016, 2019, 2020, 2024 and 2025, with the most extreme DHW values occurring in 2024 (Figure 2). The 2024 affected all archipelago groups, although its intensity varied markedly. In 2024, the strongest DHW signal was recorded in the Farquhar Group (16.8°C-weeks), followed by the Aldabra Group (12.9°C-weeks), while lower but still substantial anomalies were observed in the Alphonse Group (8.9°C-weeks), Amirantes Group (6.3°C-weeks), and Inner Islands (5.4°C-weeks). The 2016 event was also expressed across all groups but was particularly pronounced in the Inner Islands (9.3°C-weeks), Amirantes (6.6 °C-weeks), Alphonse (6.1°C-weeks) and Farquhar (6.7°C-weeks). These results indicate that Seychelles reefs are exposed to synchronised regional heat stress driven by large-scale oceanic conditions in the WIO, but that the ecological consequences of that stress could differ among reef systems.

Figure 2. Long-term weekly sea surface temperature (SST) and thermal stress time series for Seychelles (1985–2026; Polygon Middle Longitude: 51.3250; Polygon Middle Latitude: -7.0000; NOAA, 2026). The upper panel shows weekly aggregated 5km SST relative to monthly mean climatology, monthly mean maximum SST and the bleaching threshold.

National trend in live coral cover

The national trend (Figure 3) has been produced based on sites with observations in at least ≥ 7 distinct years, restricting the analysis to repeatedly monitored locations (See Method section). The national trajectory is consequently estimated toward reef systems with the strongest temporal coverage, notably the Inner Islands and Aldabra Group.

Figure 3. National trend in live hard coral cover (%) in Seychelles from 2005 to 2025, based on sites monitored in at least seven distinct years. Transparent blue lines and points show annual site-level means, dark blue line and open circles show the annual national mean.

The trend indicates a strongly non-linear trajectory in live hard coral cover over the 2004–2025 period. Coral cover was relatively low in the mid-2000s, ranging from 10–14% between 2004 and 2006, before increasing to around 20% by 2007–2009. A pronounced rise was then observed in the early 2010s, with the national mean reaching its highest levels in 2010 and remaining comparatively elevated up to 2015 with a range of 34.3–30.5%. This period was followed by an abrupt decline in 2016–2017, when mean live hard coral cover fell back to approximately 15% and then close to 10%, indicating a major national-scale setback. From 2018 onwards, coral cover showed partial recovery, increasing gradually to around 18–20% by 2019–2021, with a further increase to approximately 22% in 2023. However, this improvement was not sustained in the most recent years, and mean live hard coral cover declined again to about 17% in 2024 and 14% in 2025.

The national pattern is consistent with a reef system that experienced substantial recovery after the low-cover conditions of the early monitoring period. The reef system reached a relative peak in the early 2010s, and then underwent a pronounced decline followed by incomplete recovery. The recent decline after 2023 suggests that gains made during the post-2017 recovery phase were not secure, and that national coral cover remains vulnerable to renewed disturbance.

Reef response to thermal stress can be mediated by depth, structural complexity, nutrient conditions, wave exposure, macroalgal abundance, herbivory and juvenile coral supply and microhabitat variation across reefs at spatial scales <100 m is expected to influence patterns of adaptations (Graham et al. 2015; Robinson et al. 2019; Arif et al. 2022; Dajka et al. 2019, Guillaume et al. 2026). Thermal history and short-term temperature variability can modify bleaching susceptibility, with reefs exposed to more variable temperature regimes sometimes showing reduced coral loss or enhanced thermal tolerance (Oliver and Palumbi 2011; Langlais et al. 2017; Koester et al. 2020). This mechanism is consistent with observations from Aldabra, where lagoonal reefs experienced lower relative coral loss than seaward reefs during the 2015–2016 bleaching event, probably due to substantially higher daily temperature variability in the lagoon (Koester et al. 2020). Consequently, differences among Seychelles archipelagos in ecological response to recent thermal anomalies are likely to reflect not only variation in regional heat exposure, but also differences in geomorphology, hydrodynamics, community composition, recruitment potential and local resilience processes.

Coral bleaching on the reef wall at Astove Atoll during the 2024 bleaching event.
Source: Brighton (2024); Photo credit: Christophe Mason-Parker

Paired year-site comparison

To complement the national trend, paired-site comparisons were used to evaluate directional change among sites surveyed repeatedly over time. This approach reduces the influence of changing site composition between years by restricting comparison to matched sites. Two paired intervals were examined: a pre-2024 recovery interval, represented by repeated surveys between 2017 and 2022 for Seychelles overall coral reef extent, the Inner Islands, Aldabra Group and Amirantes Group, and between 2018 and 2023 for the Alphonse Group; and a recent interval from 2023 to the last monitored year, intended to capture the most recent change following the 2024 thermal stress event. At national scale, the paired-site results indicate recovery during the post-2016 period prior to 2024 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Mean paired change in live hard coral cover (%) for Seychelles and selected archipelago groups before and after the 2024 bleaching event, based only on matched monitoring sites surveyed in both comparison years.

Across 44 matched sites at national level, mean live hard coral cover increased from 10.7% to 15.9%, equivalent to a gain of 5.2 percentage points. Similar increases were observed in the Inner Islands, Aldabra Group and Amirantes Group. The largest mean increase occurred in the Inner Islands, where live hard coral cover rose by 5.8 percentage points across 18 matched sites, from 5.9% in 2017 to 11.7% in 2022. Aldabra showed a comparable increase of 5.6 percentage points across 12 matched sites, while the Amirantes Group increased by 4.0 percentage points across 14 matched sites. In contrast, the Alphonse Group showed a decline over its paired recovery interval, falling by 10.9 percentage points across seven matched sites between 2018 and 2023. However, despite this decrease, absolute coral cover in Alphonse remained substantially higher than in the other archipelago groups. The recent paired comparisons indicate a clear reversal in direction. At national scale, 31 matched sites showed a decline in mean live hard coral cover from 26.7% in 2023 to 20.5% in 2024, representing a decrease of 6.2 percentage points. This suggests that recent gains in coral cover were not maintained into the latest monitoring period and is consistent with the widespread thermal stress recorded in 2024. Among archipelago groups, the largest recent decline was recorded in the Aldabra Group, where mean live hard coral cover fell by 9.2 percentage points across 14 matched sites between 2023 and 2024. The Amirantes Group also showed a clear decline of 4.2 percentage points across 10 matched sites over the same interval. In the Inner Islands, the most recent paired comparison extended from 2023 to 2025, reflecting the latest available matched monitoring year, and showed a decline of 4.2 percentage points across six matched sites. The Alphonse Group also showed a decline between 2023 and 2024, but this comparison was based on a single matched site and therefore remains insufficient for robust interpretation.

Status Of The Coral Reef Archipelago Based Trend - Inner Islands

KEY NUMBERS

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2025**

Latest estimated Inners Islands mean live hard coral cover: **~20 %**

Trend in Inner Islands live coral cover: **Declining**

Summary

The Inner Islands comprise the granitic islands of Seychelles and support the most spatially extensive coral reef monitoring coverage (Figure 5). Monitoring Site density is highest around Mahé and Praslin, while temporal coverage varies substantially among islands, from single-year surveys to records extending from the 1990s to 2025. Although regional thermal stress remains the dominant driver of coral reef trajectories at this scale, local pressures also vary among islands and reefs, including fisheries, tourism and diving activity, coastal development or anchoring. Some reefs may diverge from the broader Inner Islands pattern and reflect local pressure regimes or site-specific management histories.

In 2025 estimated mean hard coral cover in the Inner Islands was 20.2% indicating a moderate but reduced coral state at archipelago scale compared to 2015 whereby coral cover was estimated at 43.4% (Figure 6; Annex 2). Regional studies show that recovery in the Inner Islands is highly contingent on depth, structural complexity, macroalgae, and local habitat condition, while recent observations from Ste Anne Marine National Park indicate that the 2024 heat event caused bleaching with generally low mortality (Andrews et al. 2024; Dajka et al. 2019; Robinson et al. 2019; Arif et al. 2022).

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of Inner Islands coral reef monitoring sites coloured by monitoring duration (years).

Inner Island trends in live hard coral cover

The 2025 mean of 20.2% indicates that live coral cover remains well below the higher levels reached in 2015, immediately before the 2016 bleaching event (Figure 6). The Inner Islands coral reefs have regained some live coral cover since the post-2017 lowest value but remains exposed to renewed climate-driven mortality.

Figure 6. Time series of thermal stress and live coral cover for the Inner Islands, Seychelles, from 2005 to 2025. The upper panel shows mean daily Degree Heating Weeks (DHW; °C-weeks; NOAA, 2026), and the lower panel shows annual live hard coral cover (%). Green points and lines represent site-level annual observations, the solid red line represents the annual archipelago mean, and the shaded band shows the 95% confidence interval around the mean. Sample size per year is indicated as the number of monitored sites (n). The 2014 mean was excluded from analysis due to uneven site representation; 2014 site-level observations were retained as transparent values.

In 2005, mean hard coral cover was 10.4 %, following extensive bleaching and coral mortality in 1998. Coral cover subsequently increased through the late 2000s and early 2010s, reaching 20.3% in 2007, 27.0% in 2010, and 37.0–38.2% in 2012–2013. The period immediately preceding the 2016 bleaching event is more variable. Mean hard coral cover declined to 14.9% in 2014, then rose sharply to 43.5% in 2015, the highest value in the series. That rapid change should be interpreted cautiously, as it reflects changes in monitored site representation rather than ecological change. No annual coral cover estimate is available for 2016, but by 2017 mean hard coral cover had fallen to 5.9%, the lowest value in the dataset. This decline coincides with the strongest DHW anomaly in the series and is consistent with a severe bleaching-related disturbance.

Following this collapse, mean hard coral cover increased to 13.1% in 2018. Between 2020 and 2022, it remained around 19.8–21.4%, indicating partial recovery. The subsequent rise to 30.5% in 2023 and 32.3% in 2024 suggested further recovery, but these years were based on limited site representation and high uncertainty.

The Inner Islands pattern is consistent with the recovery trajectories presented in Graham et al. (2024). Following the 1998 marine heatwave, reefs in the inner islands lost more than 90% of live coral cover, and subsequent trajectories diverged markedly among sites. Graham et al. (2015) showed that 12 of 21 reefs recovered towards pre-disturbance coral states, whereas nine reefs shifted towards fleshy macroalgae, with recovery favoured on deeper, structurally complex reefs with higher juvenile coral density and herbivorous fish biomass and lower nutrient loads. This helps explain why the archipelago-scale Inner Islands group integrates strong spatial and temporal variability among monitored sites (Graham et al., 2015).

The increase in coral cover from 2005 to 2013, and the high mean observed in 2015, is also consistent with published evidence of substantial recovery on many Inner Island reefs during the decade after 1998, before the marine heat wave in 2016 again caused bleaching and a decline in coral cover (Wilson et al. 2019). On north-west Mahé reefs, Vessaz et al. (2022) documented an almost fourfold increase in coral cover from 2005 to 2015, reaching 42.1% mean cover in 2015, with recovery strongly associated with *Acropora* growth forms. However, that recovery was not uniform, and the same study showed a sharp decline to 16.1% in 2017 following the 2016 bleaching event.

The ecological mechanisms underlying this uneven recovery are also well supported. Chong-Seng et al. (2014) showed that recovery bottlenecks differed among habitat states: macroalgal-dominated reefs appeared constrained by poor settlement or post-settlement survival, whereas rubble-dominated reefs showed weak progression from juvenile to adult stages, likely because unstable substrates hinder long-term survivorship. Dajka et al. (2019) found that juvenile coral densities in the Inner Islands were reduced by about 70% after the 2016 bleaching event, with especially strong declines in juvenile *Acropora*, implying that the disturbance affected both adult coral cover and the replenishment processes needed for future recovery. Together, these studies indicate that post-disturbance recovery in the Inner Islands depends not only on bleaching intensity, but also on substrate stability, macroalgal competition and juvenile survivorship (Chong-Seng et al., 2014; Dajka et al., 2019).

More recent analyses reinforce the idea that the Inner Islands remain highly heterogeneous in their resilience. Arif et al. (2022) showed that greater depth and structural complexity reduced the likelihood of climate-driven regime shifts, whereas higher macroalgal cover, nutrients and wave exposure increased it. Their predictive model also suggested that several reefs that had recovered after 1998 were still vulnerable to renewed regime shift after the 2016 event, including sites in the Ste Anne Marine National Park and Mahé sectors. Graham et al. (2024) reported that reefs that had recovered after 1998 generally remained on a coral recovery trajectory through the 2016 disturbance and documented a rare regime-shift reversal at one site, suggesting that some Inner Island reefs may now be more resilient to repeat heat stress than previously expected. However, this does not imply system-wide stability; rather, it confirms continued divergence among reefs under repeated disturbance (Arif et al., 2022; Graham et al., 2024).

The 2024 MCSS bleaching assessment from the Ste Anne Marine National Park documented intensified and prolonged heat exposure in 2024 relative to previous years, with bleaching first observed in late February and peaking between mid-April and early May (Andrews et al. 2024). Across 13 monitored sites, an average of 28.54% of live coral cover was estimated to be bleached, but average bleaching-induced mortality remained relatively low at 3.15%. The MCSS report is restricted to the Ste Anne Marine National Park and adjacent sites off north-east Mahé and focuses on short- to medium-term bleaching and recovery rather than longer-term benthic cover trajectories across the full Inner Islands. It therefore strengthens the conclusion that the 2024 event produced spatially variable local outcomes, including substantial survival from January to September 2024, but it does not overturn the broader archipelago-scale signal from the coral-cover time series. The Inner Islands archipelago wide decline from 32.3% in 2024 to 20.2% in 2025 suggests that recent thermal stress may already be constraining or reversing recent gains, even if immediate mortality was low.

Status Of The Coral Reef Archipelago Based Trend - Aldabra Group

KEY NUMBERS

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2024**

Latest estimated Aldabra Group mean live hard coral cover: **~14 %**

Trend in Aldabra Group live coral cover: **Declining**

Summary

The Aldabra Group comprises remote atolls and islands in the south-western Seychelles and is represented in the current monitoring database by sites at Aldabra Atoll and Cosmoledo, while no monitoring records are currently included for Assumption or Astove. As shown in Figure 7, monitoring effort is strongly concentrated at Aldabra, where 12 to 15 sites have been monitored between 2014 and 2024, whereas Cosmoledo is represented by 15 sites surveyed in 2014 only. Aldabra was designated a Special Reserve in 1981. As a result, local anthropogenic pressure is low, and reef trajectories in this group are likely to be shaped primarily by regional climate forcing and natural local controls rather than by chronic human disturbance. In this context, the long-term Aldabra dataset provides a particularly valuable baseline and sentinel record for coral reef change under low human-induced local pressure.

In the most recent monitoring year included in this assessment (2024) mean hard coral cover in the Aldabra Group was 14.2%, indicating a low to moderate coral-cover state and a marked decline relative to 23.9% in 2023. The latest result suggests that the gradual recovery evident through 2023 was interrupted in the most recent years. The 2024 decline coincides with the strongest thermal anomaly in the available DHW series, which peaks at approximately 13 °C-weeks, exceeding earlier heat-stress events in the NOAA record (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of Aldabra Groups coral reef monitoring sites coloured by monitoring duration (years).

Aldabra Group trends in live hard coral cover

Viewed across the full time series, hard coral cover in the Aldabra Group shows a disturbance-recovery trajectory.² The highest annual mean in the dataset occurs in 2014, at 24.0%. Coral cover then declines sharply to 12.6% in 2016, representing the lowest values in the series (Figure 8). From 2017 onwards, the time series shows a gradual and sustained increase: 14.9% in 2017, 15.8% in 2018, 18.2% in both 2019 and 2020, 19.6% in 2021, 20.4% in 2022, and 23.9% in 2023. This pattern suggests a multi-year period of recovery following the mid-2010s decline.

Figure 8. Time series of thermal stress and live coral cover for the Aldabra Groups, Seychelles, from 2005 to 2025. The upper panel shows mean daily Degree Heating Weeks (DHW; °C-weeks; NOAA, 2026), and the lower panel shows annual live hard coral cover (%). Green points and lines represent site-level annual observations, the solid blue line represents the annual archipelago mean, and the shaded band shows the 95% confidence interval around the mean. Sample size per year is indicated as the number of monitored sites (n).

Direct comparison with the earlier part of the series is also moderated by differences in sample size, with 27 observations in 2014 relating to the monitoring of Cosmoledo via the Pangea Project compared with typically 10–15 observations in later years through SIF’s yearly monitoring. The broad trajectory is clear: a sharp decline in the mid-2010s, progressive recovery through 2023, and an abrupt decline in 2024.

The decline from 23.9% in 2023 to 14.2% in 2024 shows deterioration in recent Aldabra Group coral status, and the temporal coincidence with the strongest DHW event in the series makes acute thermal stress the definitive driver of change. However, the magnitude and mechanisms of that decline likely varied within the group and should not be interpreted as implying a uniform response across all reefs.

²SIF monitoring data for 2015 were excluded from the analysis because sampling effort was lower and high coral-cover sites were under-represented (A. Koester, pers. comm.).

The broader trajectory is consistent with the documented impacts of the 2015–2016 mass bleaching event on Aldabra Atoll, which remains the best-studied component of this archipelago group. Cerutti et al. (2019) reported that Aldabra experienced continuous bleaching risk between December 2015 and June 2016, followed by substantial hard-coral loss. Koester et al. (2020) further showed that seaward reefs experienced relative hard coral reductions of 51–62%, while lagoonal coral loss was lower (34%), probably because lagoon habitats experienced higher daily temperature variability. In the present series, the decline from 24.0% in 2014 to 12.6% in 2016 is therefore fully consistent with severe bleaching-related coral mortality in the group's main atoll system (Cerutti et al., 2019; Koester et al., 2020, Koester et al., 2023).

The gradual increase from 2017 to 2023 is also consistent with published post-bleaching recovery trajectories from Aldabra Atoll. Koester et al. (2020) indicate that, between 2016 and 2019, hard coral cover increased annually on shallow reefs and that lagoonal reefs recovered particularly rapidly, reaching 93% of pre-bleaching coral cover by 2019, compared with 68% on shallow western seaward reefs and 54% on shallow eastern seaward reefs. Deeper reefs, by contrast, showed little evidence of recovery over the same period and remained dominated by turf algae and *Halimeda*. Koester et al. (2021) further documented that juvenile coral abundances tripled between 2016 and 2019 and exceeded pre-bleaching levels by 2019, supporting the interpretation that the group retained substantial replenishment potential after the 2015–2016 event (Koester et al., 2020, 2021).

Recent observational evidence from Astove and Cosmoledo provides additional context for the 2024 decline in coral cover and supports a spatially heterogeneous but severe bleaching signal within the group (Figure 9). Brighton (2024) reported that at Astove bleaching had become widespread by April 2024 across the north, the Wall and the south-western reef, extending down to approximately 35 m, with shallow mortality informally estimated at around 40% in some areas and complete mortality of *Porites cylindrica* noted along the shallow crest (Figure 9). At Cosmoledo, bleaching was described as even more extensive, with more than 85% of corals bleached, although visible mortality at the time of observation was considered lower than at Astove. Brighton (2024) attributed some of this contrast to geomorphology and depth distribution, noting that Cosmoledo coral habitats are more commonly distributed between 8–12 m on more gradually sloping reefs, whereas Astove's wall crest supports abundant shallow coral at 3–6 m. The same report also noted that lagoon corals at Cosmoledo were often fluorescing rather than fully bleached, suggesting that some habitats may have retained stronger short-term recovery potential as temperatures declined (Brighton, 2024).

Figure 9. Coral bleaching and recent mortality on the reef crest and wall at Astove Atoll during the 2024 bleaching event. Brighton (2024); Photo credit: Christophe Mason-Parker

Status Of The Coral Reef Archipelago Based Trend - Amirantes Group

KEY NUMBERS

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2024**

Latest estimated Amirantes Group mean live hard coral cover: **~ 20%**

Trend in Amirantes Group live coral cover: **Declining**

Summary

The Amirantes Group is represented in the current dataset by monitoring undertaken at African Banks, Boudeuse, D'Arros, Desroches, Etoile, Poivre, Remire, and St. Joseph Atoll (Figure 10). Monitoring spans from 2011 to 2024 and includes 43 unique sites distributed across eight island or atoll units. Monitoring is concentrated in the D'Arros - St. Joseph system and at Desroches, while several other locations are represented only by short survey windows.

The Amirantes Group coral cover peaked in 2015, declined sharply following the 2016 bleaching event, and subsequently returned to moderate levels. The group retains evidence of recovery potential, particularly on remote reefs with favourable recruitment and lower local human pressure, but repeated thermal stress and strong spatial heterogeneity mean that overall status remains unstable and should be interpreted cautiously.

Figure 10. Spatial distribution of Amirantes Groups coral reef monitoring sites coloured by monitoring duration (years).

Amirantes Group trends in live hard coral cover

Mean hard coral cover in the Amirantes Group was moderate but relatively stable from 2011 to 2014, remaining between 18.1% and 21.0%. Hard coral cover then increased markedly to 31.0% in 2015, the highest mean in the time series (Figure 11). This was followed by a sharp decline to 18.4% in 2016, after which mean cover partially recovered to 23.3% in 2017 and remained similar in 2018 at 22.8%. The time series then shows an abrupt drop to 3.3% in 2019, before returning to intermediate values in later years: 17.3% in 2022, 24.3% in 2023 and 20.0% in 2024.

Figure 11. Time series of thermal stress and live coral cover for the Amirantes Groups, Seychelles, from 2005 to 2025. The upper panel shows mean daily Degree Heating Weeks (DHW; °C-weeks; NOAA, 2026), and the lower panel shows annual live hard coral cover (%). Green points and lines represent site-level annual observations, the solid purple line represents the annual archipelago mean, and the shaded band shows the 95% confidence interval around the mean. Sample size per year is indicated as the number of monitored sites (n). The 2019 mean was excluded from analysis due to limited number of sites; site-level observations were retained as transparent values.

The 2015 increase and the 2016 decline are the clearest group-wide shifts in the record. By contrast, the low 2019 value should be interpreted with particular caution. It is based on only three sites and therefore has weak representativeness at archipelago-group scale. The absence of data for 2020 and 2021 further limits interpretation of short-term continuity across the post-2019 period. The later values from 2022 to 2024 suggest that coral cover in the group returned to moderate levels, but not consistently to the 2015 peak.

Variability among sites is high throughout much of the series. Standard deviation is large in several years, especially 2015 and 2018 (Annex 2), indicating substantial spatial heterogeneity in coral cover among reefs or islands within the group. Standard error is also elevated in years with lower sample size, particularly 2018 and 2019, reinforcing the need for caution when comparing annual means. Overall, the empirical pattern is one of moderate coral cover in the early 2010s, a pre-2016 peak, a post-bleaching decline, partial recovery, and strong interannual variability associated with uneven spatial coverage.

The thermal stress record supports this interpretation (Figure 11). The upper panel shows a pronounced DHW peak in 2016, consistent with severe regional heat stress, and another strong event in 2024. Smaller DHW pulses are evident around 2019–2020 and again in 2025, but these are notably weaker than the 2016 and 2024 events.

Interpretation of the Amirantes Group time series must account for the fact that it aggregates reefs from a geomorphologically diverse island system. The group includes reef platforms, small atolls, and the shallow submerged atoll of Desroches, with marked differences in reef extent, lagoon development, and habitat configuration among islands. D'Arros and Poivre are described as platform reefs, St Joseph and Alphonse as atolls, and Desroches as a submerged atoll, indicating that substantial natural spatial heterogeneity in coral communities should be expected across the group (Hamylton et al., 2012).

The moderate coral cover observed between 2011 and 2014 and the peak in 2015 are broadly consistent with longer-term recovery from the 1998 bleaching event reported for parts of the southern Amirantes. Hagan et al. 2008 indicates that live coral cover on fore-reef slopes in the Amirantes ranged from 7% to 26% and reefs were interpreted as recovering, with *Porites* and *Pocillopora* prominent in the recovering community. At Poivre specifically, hard coral cover was reported between 41–50% in 1992 and 1993, then 9–25% in 2005, and around 38% in 2017 despite impacts from the 2016 bleaching event (Adam et al., 2017). These comparisons suggest that some reefs within the Amirantes retained or regained relatively coral cover prior to, or in the aftermath of the 2016 event, and likely contributed to the elevated group mean recorded in 2015 (Hagan et al., 2008; Adam et al., 2017).

The decline from 31.0% in 2015 to 18.4% in 2016 is consistent with documented bleaching impacts across multiple Amirantes reefs. At D'Arros Island and St Joseph Atoll, Gadoutsis et al. 2019 recorded anomalously high sea temperatures in April 2016 and a decline in hard coral cover from 28.5% in 2015 to 14.7% in 2017, with the greatest losses on shallow reefs dominated by acroporids and pocilloporids. At Desroches, the 2017 monitoring report recorded an overall mean live hard coral cover of only 8%, explicitly linking the low cover to the 2016 bleaching event. Poivre, by contrast, was reported to keep a mean live hard coral cover of 38% in 2017, but with reduced abundance of branching *Acropora* and *Pocillopora* and dominance by *Porites*, indicating that impacts were substantial but spatially uneven within the group (Gadoutsis et al., 2019; Morgan et al., 2017; Adam et al., 2017).

A rapid assessment at Desroches during the 2010 bleaching event found 37–40% live hard coral cover at two sites, but high bleaching of *Pocillopora*-dominated communities, with *Pocillopora* comprising 70–80% of live hard coral cover and showing severe bleaching. Similarly, Gadoutsis et al. 2019 found that reefs with higher dominance of acroporids and pocilloporids suffered greater post-bleaching mortality after 2016, while deeper sites and sites with more poritidae were less affected. This provides a plausible explanation for why the group mean can remain moderate while still masking severe losses on shallow or branching-coral-dominated reefs (Adam et al., 2010; Gadoutsis et al., 2019).

The post-2016 partial recovery visible in 2017–2018 and again in 2022–2024 is also consistent with evidence that some Amirantes reefs keep recovery potential. At D'Arros and St Joseph, the post-bleaching benthic community did not shift rapidly to macroalgal or rubble dominance, coralline algae increased, and low local anthropogenic pressure was considered favourable for recovery. At Poivre, 2017 surveys reported generally good coral recruitment and high coralline algal cover at several reefs. These findings suggest that remoteness, limited chronic local stress, and recruitment potential may support recovery on at least some Amirantes reefs, although not necessarily rapid return to high coral cover everywhere (Gadoutsis et al., 2019; Adam et al., 2017). Finally, the 2024 estimate of 20.0% should be treated as provisional in status terms, because it coincides with a major DHW spike in the upper panel and may not yet fully capture delayed post-bleaching mortality.

Status Of The Coral Reef Archipelago Based Trend - Alphonse Group

KEY NUMBERS

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2024**

Latest estimated Alphonse Group mean live hard coral cover: **~ 41%**

Trend in Alphonse Group live coral cover: **Declining**

Summary

The Alphonse Group is represented in the current dataset by monitoring sites at Alphonse, Bijoutier and St François. Monitoring spans 2009–2024 and includes 39 unique sites, but temporal coverage is strongly concentrated around Alphonse Island (Figure 12).

The latest monitoring result, 47.8% hard coral cover in 2024, shows that the Alphonse Group stays one of the stronger coral-cover systems in Seychelles at archipelago scale. However, recent annual reports show that bleaching during 2024 was widespread across monitored sites, especially in lagoon reefs, and that recent average may be lower when a larger set of core sites is surveyed. Overall, the Alphonse Group appears relatively resilient, but that resilience is spatially heterogeneous and should not be interpreted as immunity to repeated marine heat stress.

Figure 12. Spatial distribution of Alphonse Groups coral reef monitoring sites coloured by monitoring duration (years).

Alphonse Group trends in live hard coral cover

At the most recent monitoring point, mean hard coral cover in the Alphonse Group was 47.8% in 2024, indicating a moderate to high coral-cover state at archipelago-group scale (Figure 13). The 2024 value remains below the series peak of 58.5% in 2020 and therefore does not indicate a clear return to the highest coral-cover levels recorded in the current dataset.

Figure 13. Time series of thermal stress and live coral cover for the Alphonse Groups, Seychelles, from 2005 to 2025. The upper panel shows mean daily Degree Heating Weeks (DHW; °C-weeks; NOAA, 2026), and the lower panel shows annual live hard coral cover (%). Green points and lines represent site-level annual observations, the solid orange line represents the annual archipelago mean, and the shaded band shows the 95% confidence interval around the mean. Sample size per year is indicated as the number of monitored sites (n).

Viewed across the full available record, hard coral cover in the Alphonse Group remains comparatively high, but the series is discontinuous and should be interpreted cautiously. Mean hard coral cover was 42.3% in 2009 and peaking at 58.5% in 2020. Mean cover then declined to 44.1% in 2021 and 41.3% in 2024. Interpretation of these changes is moderated by the structure of the dataset. Several years are based on small sample sizes, particularly 2017 ($n = 2$), 2020 ($n = 5$) and 2021 ($n = 6$), and standard deviations are high in most years, indicating substantial spatial heterogeneity among sites. The graph also shows that recent DHW anomalies were strongest in 2016 and 2024, with the 2024 peak exceeding the 2016 event. However, these major thermal stress events are not matched by a clear collapse in the annual mean coral-cover series. Instead, the data suggest that coral cover remained relatively high at group scale, despite episodic heat stress (Figure 13).

These recent reports provide a more nuanced view of the surveyed year status rather than the long-term compiled mean alone. The difference between the compiled 2024 coral-cover estimates and the lower 38.19% reported by Coupland and Andrew (2024) likely reflects not only differences in site coverage and survey design, but also the timing of monitoring. The most recent surveys in the Amirantes group were conducted between October 2023 and April 2024, spanning the progression of the warm season and the onset and peak of bleaching. Because the national and archipelago trend analyses presented in this report are based on annual mean values rather than seasonal trajectories, the estimate is not directly equivalent to a single annual status value.

The most recent *in situ* evidence comes from the two latest Alphonse annual monitoring reports. Fordham and Curd (2023) reported that overall live hard coral cover in 2022 and 2023 was approximately 53% and described coral cover as relatively stable in recent years, with no detectable decline following the 2016 bleaching event. By contrast, Coupland and Andrew (2024) reported that average live hard coral cover across all 12 core monitoring sites in 2023 and 2024 was 38.19%, lower than in prior years, and noted that bleaching severity increased as the north-west monsoon progressed, with all monitored sites showing more than 30% bleaching between January and April 2024, especially on lagoon reefs.

The longer trajectory nevertheless remains consistent with earlier evidence that the Alphonse Group recovered substantially after the 1998 mass bleaching event and that this recovery was spatially uneven across lagoon and outer-reef habitats. Early observations from Alphonse indicated that bleaching in the southern Seychelles was generally more severe on shallow outer reefs, whereas many corals survived in the Alphonse Lagoon and in lagoonal channels where water fluxes were high, suggesting that local thermal history and hydrodynamic setting have long influenced resilience within the group (Teleki et al., 1999). A broadly similar habitat contrast was later reported by Koester et al. (2020) for Aldabra, where lagoon reefs retained higher coral cover and lower relative loss than adjacent seaward reefs, supporting the interpretation that lagoon environments can, in some cases, buffer coral-cover decline under thermal stress.

More recent reports reinforce this spatial heterogeneity. Nogués et al. (2016) documented severe bleaching on the western reef of Alphonse, where approximately 90% of hard coral cover was bleached and *Pocillopora* and *Acropora* were particularly affected, while the eastern reef was described as almost unbleached, with less than 10% of hard coral cover affected. Earlier site assessments also recorded especially high live hard coral cover in the Alphonse Lagoon, reaching 74%, while sheltered sites around Bijoutier and the eastern side of Alphonse performed well, whereas the western and southern outer reef slopes of Alphonse and parts of St François had much lower cover, ranging from 5–20%. Together, these observations indicate that lagoonal reefs can contribute disproportionately to elevated archipelago-level means and may partly explain why group-wide coral cover remained comparatively high despite severe bleaching at some outer-reef sites.

Fordham and Curd (2023) found that coral community composition remained broadly consistent with previous years, with *Porites* remaining the dominant genus. Coupland and Andrew (2024) similarly reported 31 coral genera, with *Porites* comprising 47.4% of the coral assemblage, followed by *Goniastrea* (11.8%) and *Pocillopora* (6.1%). They also found high recruit abundance on outer reefs, especially for *Dipsastraea*, *Porites*, *Pavona* and *Acropora*, while lagoon sites had lower recruitment. Taken together, these findings suggest that the Alphonse Group retains appreciable recovery potential, but that present coral-cover patterns are maintained through a combination of lagoonal refugia, relatively resistant genera and continued recruitment on outer reefs.

The main uncertainty is therefore not whether the Alphonse Group retains relatively high coral cover, but how stable that condition is under repeated thermal stress. The compiled series suggests persistence of moderate to high cover through both the 2016 and 2024 heat events. However, the 2023–2024 annual report shows that widespread bleaching was already occurring across all monitored sites during the latest event, particularly in lagoon reefs, and the authors did not yet assess the full benthic consequences of that bleaching at all sites.

Status Of The Coral Reef Archipelago Based Trend - Farquhar Group

KEY NUMBERS

Latest reported year for live hard coral cover: **2019**

Latest estimated Alphonse Group mean live hard coral cover: **~ 16%**

Trend in Alphonse Group live coral cover: **Declining**

Summary

The Farquhar Group is represented in the current dataset by monitoring at Farquhar, Providence and St Pierre. Monitoring spans 2014–2019 and includes 29 unique sites, but both spatial and temporal coverage are limited and uneven (Figure 14).

Hard coral cover in the Farquhar Group appears to have remained low to moderate overall, with 2014 and 2019 both near 16%, while the 2016 peak is unlikely to represent a true group-wide increase. Recovery potential exists, particularly in lagoonal and channel-associated habitats, but the absence of post-2019 coral-cover data means the consequences of the recent 2024–2025 thermal stress events remain unresolved (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Spatial distribution of Farquhar Groups coral reef monitoring sites coloured by monitoring duration (years).

Farquhar Group trends in live hard coral cover

The Farquhar Group time series is sparse and discontinuous, with only three annual estimates available, and this strongly constrains interpretation (Figure 15). Mean hard coral cover was 16.3% in 2014, increased sharply to 47.4% in 2016, and then declined to 16.0% in 2019. On the basis of the graph alone, the series appears to show an anomalously high value in 2016 relative to both 2014 and 2019, rather than a clear monotonic trend.

Figure 15. Time series of thermal stress and live coral cover for the Farquhar Groups, Seychelles, from 2005 to 2025. The upper panel shows mean daily Degree Heating Weeks (DHW; °C-weeks; NOAA, 2026), and the lower panel shows annual live hard coral cover (%). Green points and lines represent site-level annual observations, the solid green line represents the annual archipelago mean, and the shaded band shows the 95% confidence interval around the mean. Sample size per year is indicated as the number of monitored sites (n).

The 2014 and 2019 estimates are notably similar, differing by less than 1 percentage point, which suggests that average hard coral cover in the group was low to moderate in both years. By contrast, the 2016 value is nearly three times higher than either endpoint of the series. However, this 2016 estimate is based on only five sites, and both SD and SE are high, indicating substantial spatial heterogeneity and relatively low precision around the mean (Annex 2). This implies that the 2016 value is unlikely to represent a stable group-wide condition and should be interpreted with caution.

The graph further shows that the most pronounced thermal stress events affecting the group occurred in 2016 and again in 2024, with additional moderate heat-stress pulses in 2019–2021 and 2025. The 2016 coral-cover estimate falls within the period of major thermal stress, but the limited number of observations and the discontinuous time series make it difficult to infer a direct coral-cover trajectory from the graph alone. Importantly, no coral-cover estimates are shown after 2019, so the biological consequences of the strong 2024–2025 DHW anomalies cannot yet be assessed from this dataset.

Overall, the most defensible empirical interpretation is that hard coral cover in the Farquhar Group remained around 16% in both 2014 and 2019, while the elevated 2016 value likely reflects limited or uneven site representation rather than a genuine group-wide increase during a documented disturbance period.

The low to moderate coral cover recorded in 2014 and 2019 is consistent with published descriptions of Farquhar as a reef system in which coral cover is naturally patchy and often relatively low at atoll scale. Friedlander et al. (2014) reported mean live coral cover of 16.9% in 2009 and attributed the generally poor benthic condition to a combination of limited reef habitat, localised upwelling, past bleaching and cyclones. They also showed strong spatial structuring, with coral cover highest near the northern channel and parts of the southern lagoon, while macroalgae dominated many upwelling-affected areas (Friedlander et al., 2014). This broader ecological context fits well with the 2014 and 2019 group means and supports the interpretation that Farquhar should not be expected to exhibit uniformly high coral cover across habitats.

The apparent 2016 peak in mean hard coral cover is inconsistent with the documented disturbance regime at Farquhar during that year and therefore should be treated as a likely sampling artefact or a reflection of restricted site selection. A rapid bleaching assessment undertaken between January and March 2016 recorded extensive bleaching across habitats, with more than 60% of colonies affected in the channel, about 50% in the lagoon, 50–60% on the eastern fore reef, and a maximum of 80% on the northern fore reef. *Acropora* and *Pocillopora* were especially affected, and surface temperatures exceeded 34 °C in March. This bleaching episode was followed by Tropical Cyclone Fantala in April 2016, which caused major damage to Farquhar and its surrounding environment. In that context, a high group-level coral-cover mean in 2016 is unlikely to indicate genuine reef improvement; it more plausibly reflects the small number of sampled sites and the inclusion of surviving high-cover habitats rather than group-wide status.

The 2019 value, returning to 16.2%, aligns closely with the interpretation presented in the 2019 Farquhar survey report, which concluded that mean live hard coral cover had remained low and broadly constant at around 16–17% over the preceding decade, despite severe impacts from bleaching and Cyclone Fantala. That report also documented a compositional shift since 2014 from a mixed branching, massive and encrusting coral assemblage towards one dominated more by massive and encrusting taxa, indicating substantial loss of branching corals during the 2016 event. At the same time, branching corals were still present in intermediate numbers and described as slowly recovering. This suggests that the 2019 mean does not simply represent chronic collapse, but rather a disturbed system with persistent live-coral refugia and early signs of structural reassembly in some habitats (Adam et al., 2019).

Spatial heterogeneity is central to understanding this trajectory. The 2019 survey found that lagoon patch reefs, especially near the northern channel, supported the highest hard coral cover and coral diversity, while the north-eastern and north-western fore reefs had the lowest hard coral cover and the highest turf and macroalgal cover. It also reported that lagoon patch reefs had increased hard coral cover relative to 2014, whereas exposed habitats remained more algal-dominated. Moderate coral recruitment was recorded overall, with higher recruitment associated with coralline algal-rich channels and northern reef areas. These findings indicate that recovery potential remains unevenly distributed across the atoll and is likely concentrated in sheltered or hydrodynamically favourable habitats, while exposed and upwelling-influenced reefs remain more constrained (Adam et al., 2019).

This aligns with the 2014 Pangaea assessment, which documented benthic changes from 2009 to 2014, including coral-algal phase shifts and a drop in recruitment from 14.1 to 2.9 colonies m⁻². That report identified the leeward habitat as the healthiest reef sector but also emphasised Farquhar’s vulnerability to anomalously high sea surface temperatures because some of its better coral habitats were dominated by bleaching-sensitive taxa. Taken together, the 2014 and 2019 reports suggest that Farquhar’s coral communities are structured by a combination of chronic geomorphological constraints, strong habitat differentiation, and acute disturbance from bleaching and storms, rather than by a simple linear recovery pathway (Duhec et al., 2014; Adam et al., 2019).

The recent DHW record indicates renewed severe heat stress in 2024 and further thermal stress in 2025, but there are no post-2019 coral cover data in the current series. Any inference about current status must therefore remain provisional. At present, the Farquhar Group is best characterised as a spatially heterogeneous outer-island reef system with persistently modest average hard coral cover, clear susceptibility to climate extremes, and localised but real recovery potential in sheltered reef sectors.

Conclusion

This report consolidates dispersed coral reef monitoring records into a comprehensive harmonised coral reef status dataset compiled for Seychelles, covering the period of 1994 to 2025 and integrating 11 datasets, 285 unique survey sites and 3,778 observations across the EEZ. It also establishes a standardised foundation for future national synthesis, reporting and management-oriented decision-making.

The report presents estimates and trends in coral reef live coral cover at both national and archipelago scales. At national scale, live hard coral cover followed a strongly non-linear trajectory, with recovery from the low-cover conditions of the mid-2000s, a relative peak in the early 2010s, a marked decline in 2016–2017, partial recovery after 2018, and renewed decline after 2023. This recent reversal is consistent with the strong thermal anomalies recorded in 2024, the most severe event in the available record.

Within this national structure, the Inner Islands remain central to the national picture because they contribute a large share of the long-term monitoring evidence and show clearly how coral recovery in Seychelles depends on ecological conditions rather than heat stress alone. Moreover, the present results suggest the Alphonse Group stands out for high coral cover and comparatively low accumulated thermal stress. This indicates that it may represent an important resilience node within the national reef system, potentially linked to its lagoonal and deeper reef habitats. However, this interpretation should remain cautious until it is assessed against longer and denser time series, because part of the apparent signal could still reflect differences in monitoring coverage rather than resilience.

The results also support moving beyond a narrow interpretation of reef condition based only on hard coral cover. Coral cover remains a core GCRMN indicator, but Seychelles studies increasingly show that important dimensions of reef condition are only visible when benthic, demographic and functional indicators are considered together. Juvenile coral supply, macroalgal abundance, herbivorous fish biomass and structural complexity are all relevant to recovery processes in the inner islands (Dajka et al., 2019). For national reporting, this means that future assessments would benefit from complementing hard coral cover with a broader suite of indicators that better capture ecosystem function and coral reef recovery capacity.

An important limitation of the present report is that the national monitoring framework remains heavily weighted towards shallow reef habitats. This matters because recent work in Seychelles shows that deeper habitats may support coral assemblages and functions that are not captured by shallow-water means. Off Poivre Island, upper mesophotic habitats at 30–40 m supported species-rich free-living coral assemblages with live coral cover estimated at up to 75%, and these assemblages were interpreted as contributing to habitat complexity and reef expansion on unconsolidated substrates (Samimi-Namin et al., 2025). Future national reporting would be strengthened by progressively incorporating deeper slope and mesophotic habitats where feasible.

Overall, this report provides Seychelles with a robust national baseline for coral reef status reporting while showing that national trends must be interpreted through the contrasting trajectories of the five archipelago groups. It also highlights where monitoring is already strong, where recent declines are evident, and where important gaps remain. As such, the report is both a national synthesis of current evidence and a practical reference point for strengthening future monitoring, harmonisation and reporting under the national coral reef policy framework.

Methods

Coral Reef Extent

Coral reef extent was quantified using the global 5 m resolution reef extent, geomorphic and benthic habitat maps produced by Lyons et al. (2024) through the Allen Coral Atlas. In this framework, reef extent represents the mapped footprint of shallow coral reef environments visible from satellite imagery, rather than only areas currently occupied by living hard coral. It therefore encompasses the broader shallow reef system, including associated geomorphic reef zones and benthic habitats within the reef footprint. For this report, the Seychelles reef extent layer was intersected with archipelago group and territory boundaries in GIS, and reef area was calculated for each reporting unit to provide a standardized spatial basis for national coral reef status assessment.

Data Aggregation, Compilation, Quality Assurance and Quality Control

Data included in this report were compiled from multiple sources, including monitoring datasets, institutional databases, technical reports, and published outputs. Source materials differed in format, structure, spatial and temporal coverage, and monitoring methodology. To enable national-scale analysis, datasets were harmonised into a common structure following the general principles of the GCRMN benthic data integration workflow, which standardises heterogeneous coral reef monitoring data into a synthetic database with consistent spatial, temporal, methodological, taxonomic, and metric fields (Wicquart et al., 2022). Mean live hard coral cover was extracted directly where already reported or calculated from the dataset where required after standardisation of benthic categories. Quality-control checks were applied to verify key fields such as coordinates, dates, and cover values, and only records considered suitable for analysis were retained. The resulting compilation was used as the basis for national summaries of coral reef condition, while preserving dataset provenance and attribution to original contributors.

Thermal Stress

Thermal stress was assessed using Degree Heating Week (DHW) data from the NOAA Coral Reef Watch daily 5 km product accessed via CoastWatch ERDDAP (NOAA Coral Reef Watch, 2026). Fixed sampling points were mapped against coral reef extent from the Allen Coral Atlas extent and assigned to the corresponding archipelago group (Inner Islands, Amirantes Group, Alphonse Group, Farquhar Group, and Aldabra Group). DHW was extracted for each point from the nearest 0.05° grid cell. Daily point records were used to derive archipelago-level thermal stress summaries for comparison with coral reef condition and trends.

Live coral cover Trend

National Trend

The national trend was derived from raw hard coral percent-cover observations filtered to valid records between 2004 and 2025, aggregated to a single annual mean per site, and then summarised to an annual national mean across sites. Only sites monitored in at least seven distinct years were intended to be retained for the national trend analysis, in order to focus on repeatedly surveyed locations. Annual national means were accompanied by 95% confidence intervals calculated as mean \pm 1.96 x standard error, and the plotted line and ribbon were interpolated for display purposes.

Archipelago Group Trend

Live coral cover was analysed from the national coral reef database by filtering records to hard coral observations reported as percent cover, standardising archipelago names, and restricting the dataset to the 2004–2025 period. Raw observations were first aggregated to a single site-year to reduce duplication where multiple records existed for the same site in the same year. Site identity was defined from archipelago, island, locality, and coordinates to maintain spatial consistency across repeated surveys. Annual archipelago means were then calculated from these site-year values, with associated standard deviation, standard error, and 95% confidence intervals. For visualisation only, annual mean cover and confidence intervals were linearly interpolated between the first and last monitored years within each archipelago, with no extrapolation beyond the observed monitoring period. These summaries were used to produce archipelago-specific time series of live coral cover for the Seychelles national status assessment.

For visual interpretation, temporal comparability of the archipelago mean was reviewed by expert ecologists. Where a given year was judged to be strongly affected by uneven site representation or limited replication, that year was omitted from the calculation of the archipelago mean trend and confidence interval, while the underlying site-level observations were retained in the figure as transparent values. This approach allowed the figure to preserve the full site-level information while preventing non-comparable years from driving the archipelago-scale trend.

Statistical analysis

All data cleaning, aggregation, statistical analyses and figure production were conducted in R v4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024) using RStudio. Analyses were primarily descriptive and comparative because the compiled database integrates heterogeneous monitoring programmes with uneven spatial and temporal coverage. Summary statistics were therefore calculated at the site-year, archipelago-year, and national levels. Confidence intervals were used to represent uncertainty around annual means, and interpolation was applied only for graphical continuity and was not treated as additional observed data.

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Annex 1. Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning context

The table below presents available coral reef monitoring data within the spatial and management framework of the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP). It indicates how coral reef extent, protection category and recent monitoring coverage are distributed across pre-SMSP protected areas and SMSP zoning framework, helping identify which units are supported by recent ecological data and which still require improved monitoring to inform adaptive management and reef conservation planning.

Type	Name	Area Coral (Km ²)	% Coral extent in EEZ
PRE SMSP	Port Launay Marine National Park	1.38	0.08
PRE SMSP	Baie Ternay Marine National Park	0.68	0.04
PRE SMSP	Silhouette Marine National Park	8.61	0.51
PRE SMSP	Ile Cocos, Ile La Fouche, Ilot Platte	0.64	0.04
PRE SMSP	Ste Anne Marine National Park	8.57	0.51
PRE SMSP	Curieuse Marine National Park	9.96	0.59
PRE SMSP	African Banks Marine	8.17	0.48
PRE SMSP	Mahe (Anse Faure-Fairy Land) Shell Reserve	3.33	0.20
PRE SMSP	Aldabra Special Reserve	235.85	13.92
PRE SMSP	Aride Special Reserve	2.34	0.14
PRE SMSP	Cousin Special Reserve	0.44	0.03
SMSP Zone 1	Amirantes South National Park	25.82	1.52
SMSP Zone 1	Bird Island (Ile aux Vaches) National Park	4.06	0.24
SMSP Zone 2	Amirantes to Fortune Bank Sustainable Use Area	237.42	14.02
SMSP Zone 2	Poivre Atoll Sustainable Use Area	13.49	0.80
SMSP Zone 1	D'Arros Atoll National Park	2.53	0.15
SMSP Zone 2	Farquhar Atoll Sustainable Use Area	183.80	10.85
SMSP Zone 2	Farquhar Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	451.52	26.65
SMSP Zone 2	Denis Island Sustainable Use Area	16.17	0.95
SMSP Zone 2	Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use Area	171.53	10.13
SMSP Zone 1	D'Arros to Poivre Atolls National Park	1.50	0.09
SMSP Zone 2	Desroches Atoll Sustainable Use Area	69.26	4.09
SMSP Zone 2	Alphonse Group Sustainable Use Area	92.48	5.46
SMSP Zone 1	Aldabra Group National Park	13.01	0.77
Total Coral Reef Extent under Protection	1562.55	92.24	
Seychelles Coral Reef Extent Total (Allen Coral Atlas, Lyons et al., 2024)	1693.96	100.00	

Last Reported Monitored Year ³	n site monitored	Mean Hard Coral Cover (%)
2025	1	16
2025	2	14.8
2014	10	17.8
No Data	No Data	No Data
2025	4	25.9
2025	2	8.8
No Data	No Data	No Data
No Data	No Data	No Data
2024	15	14.2
2018	10	12.9
2014	3	4.3
2013	5	17.8
No Data	No Data	No Data
2024	5	17.3
2017	10	38.2
2024	5	22.8
2019	10	16
2016	5	47.4
2023	5	12.2
2014	15	23.2
No Data	No Data	No Data
2022	4	7.5
2024	4	47.8
No Data	No Data	No Data

³Before deadline of submission for this report (February 2026)

Annex 2. Annual summary statistics for live hard coral cover (%) by archipelago group

Blank entries indicate years for which no monitoring data were available. SD= Standard Deviation; SE= Standard Error

archipelago	year	mean_coral_cover	median_coral_cover	SD_coral_cover	n_sites	SE_coral_cover
Aldabra Group	2014	23.98	26.00	13.84	27	2.66
Aldabra Group	2015				0	
Aldabra Group	2016	12.59	9.68	7.10	12	2.05
Aldabra Group	2017	14.87	14.88	8.03	12	2.32
Aldabra Group	2018	15.75	15.95	8.37	12	2.42
Aldabra Group	2019	18.19	19.14	10.05	12	2.90
Aldabra Group	2020	18.20	16.08	9.90	12	2.86
Aldabra Group	2021	19.63	16.11	10.23	12	2.95
Aldabra Group	2022	20.43	17.74	11.28	12	3.26
Aldabra Group	2023	23.85	21.01	15.54	14	4.15
Aldabra Group	2024	14.23	11.00	9.27	15	2.39
Alphonse Group	2009	42.33	39.50	26.73	30	4.88
Alphonse Group	2010				0	
Alphonse Group	2011				0	
Alphonse Group	2012				0	
Alphonse Group	2013				0	
Alphonse Group	2014				0	
Alphonse Group	2015				0	
Alphonse Group	2016	49.11	50.78	11.55	10	3.65
Alphonse Group	2017	55.38	55.38	15.38	2	10.88
Alphonse Group	2018	56.45	51.42	14.85	11	4.48
Alphonse Group	2019				0	
Alphonse Group	2020	60.17	59.17	12.37	5	5.53
Alphonse Group	2021	44.08	39.33	14.85	6	6.06
Alphonse Group	2022				0	
Alphonse Group	2023				0	
Alphonse Group	2024	41.33	40.67	13.02	11	3.93
Amirantes Group	2011	19.63	12.45	18.05	10	5.71
Amirantes Group	2012	18.26	12.50	13.99	10	4.42
Amirantes Group	2013	18.07	12.40	15.17	19	3.48
Amirantes Group	2014	21.03	16.01	13.96	13	3.87
Amirantes Group	2015	30.98	21.00	24.07	19	5.52
Amirantes Group	2016	18.44	15.92	9.26	13	2.57
Amirantes Group	2017	22.90	17.05	15.83	25	3.17

archipelago	year	mean_coral_cover	median_coral_cover	SD_coral_cover	n_sites	SE_coral_cover
Amirantes Group	2018	21.17	13.50	21.02	8	7.43
Amirantes Group	2019				0	
Amirantes Group	2020				0	
Amirantes Group	2021				0	
Amirantes Group	2022	17.28	16.61	12.42	14	3.32
Amirantes Group	2023	24.26	17.25	15.60	10	4.93
Amirantes Group	2024	20.03	15.42	11.09	10	3.51
Farquhar Group	2014	16.31	19.00	11.03	13	3.06
Farquhar Group	2015				0	
Farquhar Group	2016	47.40	51.00	15.53	5	6.95
Farquhar Group	2017				0	
Farquhar Group	2018				0	
Farquhar Group	2019	16.05	12.42	15.39	10	4.87
Inner Islands	2005	10.38	9.50	7.76	41	1.21
Inner Islands	2006	13.54	13.37	6.69	22	1.43
Inner Islands	2007	20.28	17.42	8.57	26	1.68
Inner Islands	2008	18.76	17.46	10.63	49	1.52
Inner Islands	2009	21.09	20.19	8.53	18	2.01
Inner Islands	2010	27.03	23.77	13.63	31	2.45
Inner Islands	2011	23.11	21.68	17.03	53	2.34
Inner Islands	2012	37.02	34.77	15.45	49	2.21
Inner Islands	2013	38.24	36.53	11.25	23	2.35
Inner Islands	2014				0	
Inner Islands	2015	43.49	45.48	11.05	15	2.85
Inner Islands	2016				0	
Inner Islands	2017	5.92	5.56	4.41	18	1.04
Inner Islands	2018	12.86	11.83	7.47	10	2.36
Inner Islands	2019				0	
Inner Islands	2020	19.81	24.85	11.55	5	5.17
Inner Islands	2021	21.38	14.19	16.96	6	6.92
Inner Islands	2022	20.75	16.85	14.82	34	2.54
Inner Islands	2023	30.50	25.78	22.87	6	9.34
Inner Islands	2024	32.30	28.00	19.62	9	6.54
Inner Islands	2025	20.21	16.76	14.32	34	2.46

Annex 3. CRedit contributor role table

X = involved, W = writing, and R = review

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
WILSON, Shaun	Australian Institute of Marine Science	X	X	-	-	-	R
BARRET, Léo	Bee Ecological Consulting	X	X	X	X	W	R
GENDRON, Gilberte	Bee Ecological Consulting	X	-	X	X	W	R
LUCAS, Michelle	Blue Economy Department, Ministry of Fisheries, Agriculture & Blue Economy (MoFAEB)	-	-	X	-	-	-
SORY, Abel	Blue Economy Department, Ministry of Fisheries, Agriculture & Blue Economy (MoFAEB)	-	-	X	-	-	-
HARLAY, Jérôme	Blue Economy Research Institute (BERI) - UniSey	-	-	X	-	-	-
BRIGHTON, Eleanor	Blue Safari Seychelles	-	-	X	-	-	-
Karin Moejes	CORDIO	-	-	X	-	-	-
BACHELLERIE, Max	Fregate Island	X	X	-	-	-	-
STIMPSON, Zoe	Fregate Island	X	X	-	-	-	-
ZORA, Anna	Fregate Island	X	X	-	-	-	R
ROŹNIEWSKI, Wojciech	Global Vision International (GVI)	X	-	X	-	-	-
WRIGHT, Adam	Global Vision International (GVI)	-	-	X	-	-	-
TALMA, Sheena	Independent Consultant	-	-	X	-	-	-
ADAM, Pierre- Andre	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
ANDREW, Kaeleah	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
BABOORUN, Teesha	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
BAGUETTE, François	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
BONIFACE, Ethan	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
CALABRESE, Licia	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
COLLIER, Tom	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
COUPLAND, Jack	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
CUPIDON, Annabelle	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
CURD, George	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
DUFRENNE, Vanessa	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
DUHEC, Aurélie	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	X	X	-	-	-
BURKE, Gregory	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	-	-	X	-	-	-
FERNÁNDEZ, Ariadna	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
FORDHAM, Gail	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
GENDRON, Annie	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
HARRYBA, Said	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
JEANNE, Richard	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
JUMEAU- CLARISSE, Jaymee	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
KHAN, Nasreen	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
LANGLEY, Dylan	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
LEVORATO, Elena	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
MCNEELY, William	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
MEDERIC, Emma	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	X	-	-	-
MORGAN, Mathew	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
NARTY, Christopher	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	X	-	-	-
NOGUÉS, Josep	Island Conservation Society (ICS)	X	-	-	-	-	-

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
GRAHAM, Nicholas	Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, UK	X	X	-	-	-	R
ANTHONY, Lynn	Marine Conservation Society Seychelles (MCSS)	X	-	X	-	-	-
ANDREWS, Nina	Marine Conservation Society Seychelles (MCSS)	X	-	-	-	-	-
MASON- PARKER, Christophe	Marine Conservation Society Seychelles (MCSS)	X	-	X	-	-	R
MARTATIEN, Denis	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	-
MOUMOU, Kevin	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	-
MUDALIGE, Mithila	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	-
NEVILL, John	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	-
QUATRE, Rodney	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	-
SOMERS, Rabia	Ministry of Environment, Climate, Energy and Natural Resource (MECENR)	-	-	X	-	-	R
MAICHE, Adnan	North Island	-	-	X	-	-	-

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
MIHALY, Jenny	Reef Check Foundations	X	-	-	-	-	-
COOPER, Antonia	Reef Life Survey	X	-	-	-	-	-
EDGAR, Graham	Reef Life Survey	X	-	-	-	-	-
SMIT, Kaylee	Reef Life Survey	X	-	-	-	-	-
OH, Elizabeth	Reef Life Survey	X	-	-	-	-	-
STUART- SMITH, Rick	Reef Life Survey	X	-	-	-	-	-
ANDRE, Amy	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	-	-	-	-
BULLOCK, Robert	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	X	-	-	-
GRIMMEL, Henriette	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	X	-	-	-
MONTY, Maria	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	-	-	-	-
MOULINIE, Ellie	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	-	-	-	-
POUPENAU, Dillys	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	-	-	-	-
ROBERT, Alana	Save Our Seas Foundation - D'Arros Research Centre (SOSF-DRC)	X	-	-	-	-	-
MANJENGWA, ThembeKile	Seychelles Climate Change and Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)	-	-	X	-	-	-

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
MONTHY, Adrian	Seychelles Climate Change and Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)	-	-	X	-	-	-
RENAUD, Diana	Seychelles Climate Change and Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)	-	-	X	-	-	-
ROBERT,Vania	Seychelles Climate Change and Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)	-	-	X	-	-	-
MANGROO, Rosabella	Seychelles Fisheries Authority (SFA)	-	-	X	-	-	-
BUNBURY, Nancy	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	-	-	-	-	-	R
BURT, April	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	X	X	-	-	-	-
KOESTER, Anna	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	X	X	X	-	-	R
MEDERIC, Emma	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	X	X	-	-	-	-
SANCHEZ, Cheryl	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	X	-	-	-	-	-
WALTON, Rowana	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF)	X	X	-	-	-	-
A'BEAR, Luke	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF); Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter, Cornwall Campus, Penryn, UK.	X	-	-	-	-	-
HAUPT, Philip	Seychelles Island Foundation (SIF); Kent and Essex Inshore Fisheries Conservation Authority	X	-	-	-	-	-
CARRARA, Gabriella	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)	X	X	X	-	-	R
FANCHETTE, Aishah	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)	-	-	X	-	-	-
MARIA, Joshua	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)	-	-	X	-	-	-
MOUGAL, Damien	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)	-	-	X	-	-	-

Name	Institution/ Affiliation	Data acquisition	Data analysis	Participation to workshop & meetings	Development of national chapter content	Writing of national chapter content	Review of national chapter content
ASMAN Remie	Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)	-	-	X	-	-	-
SIMS, Helena	The Nature Conservancy (TNC)	-	-	X	-	-	-
ROMAIN, Daig	United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	-	-	X	-	-	-
BERESFORD, Georgina	WiseOceans	X	-	-	-	-	-
HARDING, Ashley	WiseOceans	-	-	X	-	-	-
LEE, Oliver	WiseOceans	-	-	X	-	-	-
RENDELL, Caitlin	WiseOceans	X	-	-	-	-	-

Credit: Image courtesy of Chris Mason Parker
Tourism Department

